

POSSIBLE STRATEGY OF UZBEKISTAN FOR INTEGRATION INTO THE PROCESSES OF THE FOURTH INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION: A CHOICE BETWEEN TECHNOLOGICAL ZONES OR AN INDEPENDENT PATH

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The term Industry 4.0 originated in Europe in 2011 and was announced at one of the industrial exhibitions in Hannover as widely used by the German government in the production of information technology. A dedicated team of officials and experts has developed a strategy for transforming German industrial enterprises into smart ones. Following this example, other countries began to introduce new technologies, and now the idea of "Industry 4.0" is beginning to conquer the world.

Let's see what the term "Industry 4.0" means. There is a more general term for the Internet of Things or the Internet of Everything, which refers to connecting simple things to the existing Internet. This applies to everything — household appliances, cars, buildings and of course, industry and agriculture.

Thus, Industry 4.0 is the application of the IT factor in production. To see an industry example of this, imagine a piece of equipment that takes the software needed for a workflow from the network itself, analyzes its own obsolescence, quickly orders parts from stock, and installs them on its own to increase its productivity. The main feature of Industry 4.0 is a different system for achieving a specific goal with minimal human intervention in the work of all components of the production process, communication with people. The time has come for the emergence and growth of the Industry 4.0 market. As a result, many companies that have embarked on the principles of a new era of industry will benefit. However, to become the company of the future, you need to start moving faster than others now.

Although the global industry is on the cusp of Industry 4.0, all of its technologies can only be applied by those who have internalized the achievements of the previous Industrial Revolution, Industry 3.0. As for the economy of Uzbekistan, it must be admitted that we are now in the process of transition from Industry 2.0 to Industry 3.0. This is a serious obstacle to the full modernization of the Uzbek industry. Of course, awareness and understanding of this problem is a step forward.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev announced 2018 in our country as the Year of Active Entrepreneurship, Support for Innovative Ideas and Technologies. In addition, the President outlined a strategic plan to include Uzbekistan in the list of 20 developed countries of the world. Achieving this ambitious and global goal will require a radical transformation of the economy and industry of Uzbekistan and the

widespread application of the principles of Industry 4.0. Of course, the introduction of new conditions and the announcement of new initiatives will not solve the problems we face. To achieve specific goals, it is advisable to take the following practical steps:

Firstly, involve foreign experts in the preparation of the relevant parts of the draft Industry 4.0 Strategy and work with them in Germany, USA, Canada, Japan, China, South Korea. Study experience, preparation of the regulatory framework, legal documents to support the introduction of new technologies.

Secondly, the main driving forces of society are the systematic collaboration of government, higher education institutions and the business community in scientific research. Ensuring the transformation of universities into large business incubators, in which students, teachers and professors create new enterprises based on the technologies created in them. The state should take on the role of a venture investor. Business representatives, together with higher educational institutions, take on the task of developing fundamental and applied research both independently and in the laboratories of higher educational institutions.

Thirdly, it is necessary to develop a National Program of Technological Development for the next 15-20 years, which will create conditions for regional and even global leadership of Uzbekistan, and to start its immediate implementation. Within the framework of the project, special tasks will be set for modern higher education institutions — they will have to take on a new entrepreneurial function and create an economic and cultural environment that is 10-15 years ahead of others. Only then will higher education be able to prepare people for the future and not for the past.

In conclusion, the world is undergoing such fundamental changes that there has never been such a great opportunity or such a great potential threat in world history. The narrow-mindedness and “non-revolutionary” thinking of some industry leaders can hinder development strategies. Artificial intelligence, robotics, the popularity of additive technologies, nanotechnology, biotechnology and much more are becoming an integral part of everyday life. If we want to be at the forefront of these changes, we need to better understand the direction in which technological progress is expected in the coming years and what global innovations are expected in the future, and take an active part in creating them.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Morrar R., Arman H., Musa C. The Fourth Industrial Revolution (Industry 4.0): Prospects for Social Innovation

2. Luppicini R. Ethical impact of technological achievements and applications in society. Hershey, PA, 2012
3. Brignolfson E., McAfee E. The second era of machines. Work, progress and prosperity in the era of the latest technology. New York: W.W. Norton & Company, 2014
4. Geiger R., Sa C. Using the wealth of science: universities and prospects for economic growth. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard. 2013
5. Tyler SS, Hansen H. Form seeking: a look at the field of organizational aesthetics // Journal of Management Research. 2005.
6. Boer D. Social and innovation policy for industry 4.0. Tübingen, Germany: University of Tübingen. Eberhard Karl. 2015